

ASPECTS Data Management Plan

Version 1.0

22 May 2021

Funded by the European Union

HISTORY OF CHANGES

Version	Publication date	Changes
1.0	22.05.2021	▪ Initial version

Action Number: 101080167

Action Acronym: ASPECTS

Action title: Quantum thermodynamics of precision
in electronic devices

Date: 08/05/2023

DMP version: 1.0

1. Introduction

This report outlines the key aspects of the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the ASPECTS project. We follow the template provided by the European Commission for the development of a DMP. We also make use of resources from within the ASPECTS Consortium (hereafter referred to simply as the Consortium), including data management support for institutional libraries, access to generic repositories, and institutional policies on open-access publication.

The DMP describes the data generated by the project, how it will be gathered, curated and preserved, in compliance with legal requirements under EU Regulation 2016/679¹, as well as the FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability) principles ensuring all data that can be shared is made available in a manner that is easily findable, accessible, interoperable and permits reuse.

All Consortium partners are in charge of guaranteeing that their own data processing activities comply with GDPR and relevant national law, as well as with responsible research and innovation principles for the ethical conduct of research. As the Coordinator, Trinity College Dublin (TCD) will resort to the Data Protection Office at TCD for legal advice where necessary. Any issues concerning the compliance of project activities with legal and ethical guidelines should be notified to the Coordinator as soon as possible.

This DMP is a "dynamic" document, meaning that it will be reviewed and revised during the project, if necessary.

2. Data Summary

2.1 Purpose of data generation and collection

As outlined in the Description of the action (DoA), ASPECTS is a fundamental science project. Its main scientific objective is to exploit quantum coherent processes occurring in nanoscale circuit devices to obtain a thermodynamic advantage for precision measurement. Therefore, the main purpose of collecting data is to record the results of experimental measurements or theoretical calculations, which can then be shared and synthesised among the consortium partners, and ultimately communicated to the wider scientific community, in order to advance human understanding and control of Nature. However, ASPECTS has numerous other tasks in support of its main goal, including the appropriate administration of grant funds, management of Consortium team members, organisation of scientific and public events, and the creation and exploitation of intellectual property (IP). In pursuit of these goals, the following different categories of data will be collected:

Personal data: Names and contact details of individuals, including Consortium personnel, attendees at events organised by the Consortium, and external experts and collaborators.

¹ REGULATION (EU) 2016/679 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation), <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1563992536948&uri=CELEX:32016R0679>.

Financial/administrative data: Financial data (company name, address, VAT number) of Consortium partners, which is needed to administer and distribute grant funds.

Dissemination and exploitation (DEC) data: Data collected to support and record dissemination and exploitation activities, including a database of events organised and attended by Consortium members, a database of publications, records of intellectual property (IP) generated during the project, and market characterisation data (sizes, trends, competitors, existing patents, standards, regulations, prices, etc.).

Research data: Data generated by research activities, which is necessary to advance the scientific objectives of ASPECTS.

Personal data and financial/administrative data is considered confidential, and will be shared only with Consortium members or administrative staff (human resources & finance offices) at the partner institutions as necessary for the management and administration of the project. All personal data will be processed in accordance with institutional data protection policies and in full compliance with EU law (especially Regulation 2016/679¹) and UK law.

All DEC and research data, including raw data and any resulting aggregated data, will be made available for sharing within the Consortium. All research data will be assessed for its potential for commercial exploitation by the ASPECTS management board. Any research data not tethered to IP will be aggregated and disseminated via standard methods for scientific dissemination: peer-reviewed publications, conference proceedings and presentations, workshops, and seminars. The Consortium's commitment to Open Science means that all publications will be made open access, providing access to the data and results not only to the scientific, teaching, and research community but also to industry and the general public, as appropriate. Research data necessary for scientific reproducibility (including code and data needed to generate plots) will be made open access via appropriate repositories. See Section 3 for details of how these data will be made findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable.

The research outlined in the DoA builds upon previous work by the Consortium members. Therefore, some existing research data generated by previous activities of Consortium partners will be re-used. As outlined in the Consortium Agreement (CA), no background IP is brought to the project.

2.2 Types, format and size of collected data

Personal and financial/administrative data will mainly be stored and processed using proprietary Microsoft software in formats such as .docx.

DEC data will be processed using proprietary database software (Notion, Microsoft Excel, Google Sheets), and stored using the interoperable .csv format.

Research data consists of two sub-categories, experimental and theoretical data.

- **Experimental data** consist of measurements of current and radio-frequency cavity signals as a function of time, gate voltages and magnetic fields; measurements of scattering parameters of microwave networks, time traces of voltages recorded with fast acquisition cards, and data derived from these measurements after real-time signal processing and post-processing. Such experimental data, together with the exact measurement configuration (properties of physical instruments and virtual instruments exposed to the software interface by measurement drivers), are stored in hdf5

format using proprietary software (Keysight Labber) or Python scripts. The measurement code used to acquire the data (scripts, instrument drivers) is stored in a private repository.

- **Theoretical data** consist of executable computer code (including Python scripts and Mathematica notebooks), and floating-point numbers obtained from numerical simulations stored as lists in .dat files.

We expect that during the course of the project, several thousands of measurements and several thousands of numerical simulations will be performed. The majority of the data generated will be in text or image format, so the total storage requirements will be relatively low, with individual files typically in the kB or MB size range.

2.3 Data utility

The primary user of the data generated by ASPECTS will be Consortium members themselves. Raw and aggregate data will be shared within the Consortium in order to make progress towards achieving the scientific objectives of the project.

Outside of the Consortium, the research data will primarily be of interest to other scientific researchers working in similar scientific areas. Aggregated project results will be accessible to external users in through standard scientific dissemination measures, i.e. preprints, publications, conference talks, and seminars. General information on the Consortium and its scientific progress, which of use for external researchers and EU administrators, will also be summarised on the ASPECTS website (www.aspects-quantum.com)

Raw data necessary to reproduce the disseminated scientific results will be made accessible via appropriate repositories (see Section 3). If appropriate, external researchers may also request further details or more granular data from individual Consortium partners. Access to this research data will be subject to data sharing agreements handled by the relevant Technology Transfer Office (TTO), as the fundamental rights to the generated data will rest with the generator of the data.

3. FAIR data

3.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

ASPECTS is committed to make data as open as possible, following guidelines which guarantee that openly published data are findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR). Importantly, datasets generated by the Consortium will be deposited in suitable repositories, which will allow their identification with persistent identifiers (PIDs). This is described in detail in section 3.2.

All published data will be provided with detailed metadata following the Dublin Core schema and will be assigned digital object identifiers (DOIs). Details such as the funder name, programme name and grant number as well as links to associated publications and related sources will be provided.

Keywords to assure that the datasets deposited in the repositories designated in section 3.2 are identifiable and discoverable will be added. Such repositories support full text indexing of all terms within files and therefore full text searching. Standardised terms to facilitate specific searches will be used. Where applicable, these terms will include, but not restricted to, OECD Fields of Science, EC research areas, themes and missions.

3.2. Making data accessible

Repositories

Datasets will be deposited in TARA (Trinity's Access to Research Archive) and the open-access Zenodo repository. Both repositories are available immediately and at no cost: TARA is accessible to all ASPECTS staff employed at TCD, and Zenodo is accessible to any individual.

Both repositories automatically assign PIDs in the form of handles and, in the case of Zenodo, DOIs. Zenodo assigns a DOI to all publicly available uploads, in order to make content easily and uniquely citable and this repository also makes use of the OAIPMH protocol (Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting) to enable the content search through the use of defined metadata.

Preprints of all publications will be placed on the open-access repository [arXiv](#). After peer review and publication, the Authors Accepted Manuscript (AAM) of all publications (i.e. the version incorporating any changes as a result of peer review) will be uploaded to the arXiv. This final author version will include a link to the DOI of the final version published by the journal. In addition, the arXiv automatically assigns a permanent, separate DOI to all submissions.

Data

In accordance with the Horizon Europe Grant Agreement (GA), results arising from this project will be kept by the beneficiary that created them. To prevent or settle any ownership disputes, beneficiaries will keep detailed documentation of research activities to show how and when the results were generated.

We will ensure that all data needed for the scientific reproducibility of our results is made publicly available. However, data that will be re-used for further research towards the Consortium's objectives may not be made publicly available until after the aforementioned research is completed. This avoids relinquishing any competitive advantage to scientific or industrial competitors of the Consortium. All results will also be assessed for intellectual property (IP) potential by the ASPECTS management board in conjunction with TCD's Transfer of Ownership (TOO) and the AMBER business team before being made publicly available, to ensure potential exploitable IP is captured. Key exploitable results not tethered by IP will be published on the Horizon Results Platform to ensure further accessibility and aid in connecting with stakeholders that can bring the project to a later stage of development, if appropriate. Datasets which are deemed suitable for open publication will be made openly accessible through Zenodo at the same time as the associated AAM is deposited on arXiv.

For all publications we will retain copyright of the AAM and will apply a Creative Commons Attribution license to the AAM. Efforts will be made to publish in open access journals, with particular consideration given to publishing through Open Research Europe. All AAMs of peer-reviewed publications will be uploaded to the open-access repository arXiv.org, as well as institutional open access repositories such as TARA and ORA and the open-access Zenodo repository. For each publication, the raw data, the analysis scripts used to produce the data in the figures, and the data in the figures (in .dat format) will be uploaded to the repositories.

Importantly, TCD is able to provide a data sharing platform via the TCD institution Microsoft Cloud service, which can grant individuals access with either read-only or editing privileges. Security

measures such as password protection will be implemented, and access will be restricted to only those who require it.

Embargoes will be strictly limited in their application, but may be applied to data until publication of the results of the data analysis if it is considered necessary. After conducting a thorough data cleaning and verification process, the open or temporarily embargoed data outputs will be uploaded from the project's shared folder to appropriate institutional or external trusted repositories, like Zenodo. As described before, these outputs will be linked to associated outputs using standardized classification and PIDs like handles and DOIs. Published data will be packaged in paper-centric replication packages (RP), together with README files in which the RP structure and contents will be detailed.

There will be no restrictions placed on any data that the project makes open.

Metadata

To enhance findability, all published data will be provided with metadata prepared according to relevant standards. Data deposited in GitHub, Zenodo, ORA and TARA will be accompanied by Dublin Core metadata, which complies with the OpenAIRE Guidelines for Data Archives and uses the DataCite metadata standard. This includes the funder name, programme name and grant number as well as links to associated publications and related sources. These metadata are optimised by their repositories for exposure on the internet for discovery and harvesting purposes.

3.3. Making data interoperable

The Consortium is committed to ensuring that all data generated from this project are fully interoperable. In cases where proprietary formats lack openness or compatibility with other systems, our approach will involve utilizing exports in formats that are interoperable. This means that we will opt for formats such as .pdf, .txt., .dat, and .csv, which are designed to work seamlessly across a range of platforms, rather than relying on formats that are limited to a single system or application.

The metadata will comply with the FAIR principles by utilizing vocabularies that align with these principles. For specific terms, open and external vocabularies such as Open Definition for license, FundRef for funders, and OpenAIRE for grants will be referenced. In addition, the metadata will feature qualified references to other metadata, and all external metadata that is referenced will be associated with a resolvable URL.

3.4. Increasing data re-use

As mentioned in Sec. 3.2, we will apply a Creative Commons Attribution licence to ASPECTS datasets shared on public repositories such as Zenodo, for future data reuse. Data will be made available once it has been published in project deliverables or other publications, as deemed appropriate by partners whose work it concerns. The specified license permits interested third parties to reuse openly available data.

Requests for unpublished data will be reviewed by the project team on a case-by-case basis. Access to this data will be subject to data sharing agreements handled by the relevant Technology Transfer Office (TTO), as discussed in Sec. 2.3.

All data collected or generated during the project will be reviewed by the project team and checked for duplicates and inconsistencies before being made publicly available. Each measurement file will

receive a unique identifier to ensure future findability and reusability. Data will be cleaned prior to analysis and sharing.

4. Other research outputs

In addition to data, ASPECTS will generate software used for data analysis and numerical simulations. This software will be stored in Github repositories to facilitate sharing. Code used for data analysis and simulations will be shared among the Consortium via project-specific repositories. Wherever possible, these repositories will be made publicly available to researchers outside the Consortium. All software necessary for scientific reproducibility of the results will be made publicly available at the same time as the associated preprint is uploaded to arXiv. Software that will be re-used for further research towards the Consortium's objectives may not be made publicly available until after the aforementioned research is completed, in order to avoid relinquishing competitive advantage to scientific or industrial competitors of the Consortium. All software will also be assessed for intellectual property (IP) potential by the ASPECTS management board in conjunction with TCD's Transfer of Ownership (TOO) and the AMBER business team before being made publicly available, to ensure potential exploitable IP is captured.

Open-access tensor-network software produced as part of WP1 will be deposited on the publicly available repository at <https://github.com/aspects-quantum/thermo-precision>. This will be assigned a permanent DOI using the integration between Zenodo and Github.

All publicly available software will be published following the FAIR principles and procedures outlined in Section 3 for data. In particular, all measures described in Section 3 regarding metadata, descriptive file names, and the use of interoperable file formats (either .c or .py for C and Python code, respectively), will apply to published software as well. All documentation and information on software dependencies will be provided in the respective repositories within README files.

5. Allocation of resources

As described above, the ASPECTS project will use free repositories (Zenodo, GitHub, TARA, ORA, arXiv), and therefore making data FAIR will not incur any costs.

Some costs may be incurred by publishing in open access journals. Some of these costs are provided for by funding for ASPECTS, as outline in the GA. Any further costs for open access publication will be covered by institutional agreements with the respective publishers (e.g. via the IReL consortium of which TCD Library is a member), or via external funds, e.g. from other grants that also fund related work of the Consortium members. Where possible, priority will be given to open access journals that have minimal or zero publication costs (e.g. Quantum, SciPost, Open Research Europe).

Individual Consortium partners will handle their own data generation and curation, in line with the Consortium Agreement. Specific data transfer agreements may be developed between relevant participants. The Coordinator will help the data management process, and will seek guidance from TCD's Library or TTO. The use of public, free, and permanent repositories will ensure the long term preservation of the data and software without additional effort or cost beyond the lifetime of the project.

6. Data security

Beneficiaries are expected to use their local Information Technology Services (ITS) units for managing data, which includes accessing storage and processing services as well as backup services. All ITS units offer secure storage and transfer of files. In cases where the data is highly sensitive or of significant value, the relevant researcher will collaborate with the local ITS unit to receive guidance and recommendations on the best practices for storage, backup, and recovery.

To support the sharing of relevant data within the Consortium, TCD is able to facilitate file sharing and limited backup through its Microsoft Cloud service, which will be managed by the Coordinator. This system includes encryption and access management features.

Institutional repositories such as TCD's TARA will be used for data long term storage. TARA uses DSpace-generated preservation metadata and checksum reporting. TARA is backed up on a nightly basis following standard database maintenance and backup procedures, as well as institutional security protocols. The deposit agreement allows for file format migration if it becomes necessary in the future.

7. Ethics

The Consortium currently has no knowledge of any ethical or legal complications that may arise during the generation, processing, or sharing of the data in accordance with the Data Management Plan (DMP) and other obligations. However, as this document will be updated whenever necessary, any ethical or legal concerns that may arise will be evaluated continuously. The data sharing process will be carried out in accordance with the DMP and other pertinent obligations.

8. Other issues

As of now, there are no additional local regulations or procedures that have been identified. However, this document will be revised as deemed necessary.